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Residual Solvents Quantitation Method for Lasmiditan Hemisuccinate API by HSGC-FID

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ABSTRACT

Lasmiditan Hemisuccinate (LDT) is an innovative medication designed for the treatment of acute migraines, operating by activating 5-HT_{1F} receptors found within the central nervous system. The synthesis of LDT necessitates the use of various solvents. According to regulatory standards, assessing the levels of residual solvents in drug substances is imperative in API (Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients). Present study concentrates on the evaluation and validation of a method for quantifying residual solvents like methanol, acetone, isopropyl alcohol, dichloromethane, methyl ter. butyl ether, n-hexane, ethyl acetate, n-heptane in LDT. Analysis was conducted using a DB-1 capillary column, measuring 60 meters in length with an internal diameter of 0.32 mm and a film thickness of 5 μ . The oven temperature was set to 65°C for 12 minutes, followed by a ramping rate of 15°C per minute to reach 85°C, where it was held for 5 minutes. Subsequently, a second ramping phase increased the temperature at a rate of 10°C per minute until it reached a final temperature of 220°C, which was maintained for 5 minutes. The injector temperature was maintained at 200°C and nitrogen was utilized as the carrier gas with 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP) diluent serving as the sample solvent. A suitable sensitive and robust HSGC-FID method is developed for quantitation of residual solvents with flame ionization (FID) detector. The evaluated method can be applied to analyse of solvents present in a various range of APIs, intermediates.

Keywords: Residual solvents, Lasmiditan Hemisuccinate, Method validation

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INTRODUCTION

Residual solvents, which lack therapeutic value, present risks of toxicity and undermine the quality and stability of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) or drug products [1-4]. Despite their insignificance, completely removing solvents via conventional manufacturing methods like elevated process temperatures or reduced pressure proves challenging. Therefore, minimizing their presence is crucial. The International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q3C has set permissible daily exposure limits (PDE) for various solvents, categorizing them into four classes based on toxicity and environmental hazards. Class I solvents include 5 residual solvents, Class II comprises 29 solvents, and Class III covers 26 solvents. Although Head Space Gas Chromatography (HSGC) is frequently employed for residual solvent quantification, it effectively mitigates interference from degradation and decomposition products. However, it necessitates larger sample loads and extended analysis times due to prolonged equilibration periods and solvent evaporation. Nonetheless, the headspace technique provides the advantage of bypassing direct liquid or solid injections.⁵⁻¹¹

Lasmiditan hemisuccinate (LDT) is a new acute migraine treatment that works by activating 5-HT_{1F} receptors, which are serotonin receptors observed in the central nervous system.¹²⁻¹⁵ It is highly selective for these receptors and does not affect other types of receptors and it will reduce to cardiovascular risk factors.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ It works by activating serotonin receptors in the brain, which helps to reduce the inflammation and pain associated with migraine. This important API synthesis involves the eight solvents i.e. acetone, Isopropyl alcohol, dichloromethane, n-hexane, isopropyl acetate, n-heptane and they need to control. The detailed literature search does not shown the any specific methods related to the analysis of residual solvents by HSGC for LDT. In this research article, we discussed a detailed method development and validation of an HSGC robust analytical method for determination of residual solvents. The chemical structure of LDT is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of LDT

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Chemical, material, and reagents

LDT was synthesized in Uquifa India Private Limited. (Hyderabad, Telangana, India). Acetone, isopropyl alcohol, dichloromethane, n-hexane, ethyl acetate, isopropyl acetate, and n-heptane were acquired from Merck (India), while 1-Methyl-2-Pyrrolidinone (NMP) was obtained from Spectrochem (Mumbai, India).

Instrumentation

The method development and validation studies utilized an Agilent Technologies 6890N HSGC system equipped with a Flame Ionization Detector and a headspace sampler (Agilent Technologies G1888). Data acquisition and chromatographic data integration were performed using EZ-Chrome software. Sample weighing was conducted on a Mettler Toledo XP205 model balance, and micro-pipettes ranging from 100 to 1000 μ L from Borosil were employed.

Gas chromatographic parameters

60 m x 320 mm, 5.0 μ film thickness DB-1 (100% dimethylpolysiloxane) capillary GC column to achieve proper separation. DB-1 column was manufactured by J&W Scientific (Agilent Scientific Technologies, Wilmington, DE, USA). The detailed method parameters mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1: HSGC Chromatographic conditions of LDT

Instrument	: A gas chromatograph equipped with headspace and FID
Ionization detector	: Flame Ionisation Detector
Column type	: DB-1 60 m x 320 mm, 5.0 μ , (Part No.:123-1065)
Initial temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	: 65
Initial hold time (min)	: 12
Ramp rate 1 ($^{\circ}$ C)	: 15
Temperature 1 ($^{\circ}$ C)	: 85
Hold time 2 (min)	: 5
Ramp rate 2 ($^{\circ}$ C)	: 10
Temperature 2 ($^{\circ}$ C)	: 220
Hold time 3 (min)	: 5
Run time (min)	: 34.83
Injector mode	: Spilt
Split ratio	: 1:20
Carrier flow (mL/min)	: 1.5
Injector temperature	: 200
Detector temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	: 260
Carrier Gas	: Nitrogen
H ₂ flow (mL/min)	: 30
Air flow (mL/min)	: 300
Makeup flow (mL/min)	: 30
Head space Operating conditions	
Oven temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	: 90
Loop temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	: 100

Transfer line temperature (°C)	: 110
GC cycle time (min)	: 40
Vial equilibration time (min)	: 20
Injection time (min)	: 1.0
Vial fill volume	: 2 mL
Shake vials	: Level-3

Preparation of standard and sample solution

A composite standard stock solution of all the specified solvents prepared in periodic dilutions to attain a final concentration of 3000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ methanol, 5000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ acetone, 5000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ isopropyl alcohol, 690 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ dichloromethane, 5000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ methyl ter. butyl ether, 290 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ n-hexane, 5000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ ethyl acetate, 5000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ n-heptane in 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP). The blank and standard solution vials was prepared with 2.0 mL of NMP, and the sample vials were prepared with 200 mg per 1.0 mL NMP.

Method validation

Validation of the method involved assessing key parameters such as specificity, limit of detection, limit of quantitation, linearity, accuracy, intermediate precision, system suitability, and method precision for residual solvents, in accordance with the ICH harmonized tripartite guideline (2005).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

HSGC method development

In the development of methods using HSGC, essential considerations include selecting the sample solvent, detector, column, carrier gas, and optimizing headspace and chromatographic conditions. The developed method should exhibit specificity, sensitivity, robustness, and suitability for quality control (QC) purposes. Below, we discuss these critical parameters in detail.

Detector and Carrier gas selection

The method utilized a flame ionization detector (FID) due to its excellent sensitivity. Nitrogen was chosen as the carrier gas for its cost-effectiveness compared to helium.

Column selection

The choice of GC column plays a crucial role in the development of HSGC methods. Typically, a stationary phase containing 6% cyanopropylphenyl and 94% dimethylpolysiloxane (DB-624) is suitable for the majority of residual solvents. The DB-624 column is mid-polar nature and high temperature limit as compare to other polar columns like DB-Wax. Moreover, it helps the polar solvent to elute at longer retention times as compare to non-polar column (DB-1). As we targeted to develop sensitive, rugged HSGC method, a DB-1 column (60 m \times 0.32 mm, 5.0 μ film thickness) was selected. The specimen chromatogram shown in Figure 2. During method development, we

encountered challenges in separating acetone and isopropyl alcohol. Ultimately, the resolution of these solvents in the evaluated method was approximately 2.5. We also tried the separation in DB-624 (94% dimethyl polysiloxane) column to understand the effect of the stationary phase. In DB-624 column the resolution is decreased from 2.5 to 1.2. Hence, the DB-1 column is selected for the separation residual solvents in LDT.

Figure 2: Specificity chromatogram of LDT residual solvents Solvent Names: a) 3000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of methanol b) 5000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of acetone c) 5000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of isopropyl alcohol d) 690 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of dichloromethane e) 5000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of methyl ter. butyl ether f) 290 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of n-hexane h) 5000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of ethyl acetate i) 5000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of n-heptane)

Selection of sample solvent

To verify the sample solubility and to select the sample solvent, a series of solvents like tried like Dimethyl formamide (DMF), Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP). As there was minimal interference at the retention times of the targeted solvents and high boiling point, NMP considered as sample solvent.

Chromatographic conditions

HSGC method can developed in two ways for selecting oven programs. One approach is kept the low oven temperature followed by gradient oven temperature and in second approach is isothermal elution. At initiation of method, development has thrown a challenge where most of the solvents are eluting early. As we are interested in extending the retention time of the solvents, we

selected the first strategy. In first strategy, we started the development and finalized 65 °C temperature as initial oven temp and hold time for 15 minutes. After that a gradient was applied i.e. 15 °C/min to 85 °C and hold for the 5 minutes, to improve the resolution of acetone and isopropyl alcohol. The oven temperature 10 °C/min increment to 220 °C with 5 min hold time to elute other unknown impurities and 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP). The nitrogen flow rate was finalized at 1.5 mL/min with definite run time of about 35 minutes.

Headspace parameters optimization

Generally, the Headspace oven temperature similar to the boiling point of specified residual solvents. The loop temperature and transfer line temperature were maintained 10–15 °C higher than the oven temperature to mitigate carryover issues. The headspace oven temperature was kept at 90 °C, because of all residual solvents have close to that boiling point. The loop line and transfer line temperature were kept to 100 °C and 110 °C, where the evaporated solvent need to reach the injector. The equilibration time of vial was set to 20 min. Table 2 outlines the specific headspace parameters.

Table 2: Specificity data of residual solvents in LDT

Solvent name	Retention time (minutes)	
	Spiked sample	Un-spiked sample
Methanol	3.98	3.96
Acetone	6.30	6.26
Isopropyl alcohol	6.68	6.64
Dichloromethane	7.49	7.47
Methyl <i>tert</i> butyl ether	8.17	8.16
n-Hexane	8.96	8.95
Ethyl acetate	12.60	12.59
n-Heptane	18.77	18.78

Method validation

The final method underwent validation as per the requirements outlined in the ICH guidelines

Specificity

Specificity was assessed by injecting a blank, individual standard solutions of residual solvents, and spiked solvent sample solutions. It, does not have any shakles at the retention time of targeted residual solvents or any other unknown peaks. Hence, the method is specific. The retention time (in minutes) of methanol, acetone, isopropyl alcohol, dichloromethane, methyl *tert* butyl ether, n-hexane, ethyl acetate and is n-heptane is 3.96, 6.26, 6.64, 7.47, 8.16, 8.95, 12.59, 18.78 respectively. The retention time of diluent (NMP) was 33.81 minutes. A specimen chromatogram of each individual solvent chromatogram at specification level is shown in Figure 2 and retention times for spiked and un-spiked sample were shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Linearity data of residual solvents in LDT

Solvent name	Correlation coefficient	Slope	Intercept	% Y-Intercept at
Methanol	1.000	0.00043	-286.02	-0.0037
Acetone	0.999	0.00016	-183.51	-0.0006
2-Propanol	0.998	0.00061	-312.69	-0.0036
Dichloromethane	0.999	0.00092	-36.61	-0.0049
Methyl <i>tert</i> butyl ether	0.998	0.00007	-322.14	-0.0036
n-Hexane	0.996	0.00003	-17.85	-0.0001
Ethyl acetate	0.999	0.00029	-341.90	-0.0004
n-Heptane	0.997	0.00005	-415.85	-0.0004

Method sensitivity

The LOQ limit found as $911 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for methanol, $1513 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for acetone, $1498 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for isopropyl alcohol, $192 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for dichloromethane, $1503 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for methyl *tert* butyl ether, $91 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for n-hexane, $1517 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for ethyl acetate and $1499 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for n-heptane. The LOQ chromatograms were shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: LOQ solution chromatogram of LDT residual solvents Solvent Names: a) $911 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of methanol b) $1513 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of acetone c) $1498 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of isopropyl alcohol d) $192 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of dichloromethane e) $1503 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of methyl *ter.* butyl ether f) $91 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of n-hexane h) $1517 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of ethyl acetate i) $1499 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of n-heptane

Linearity and range

The calibration curve plotted from LOQ level to 150 % level w.r.t to specification limit. The method exhibited linearity across the specified range, with correlation coefficient (R²) values exceeding 0.99 for all specified solvents.. The linearity graph provided in Figure 4 and Table 3. Therefore, the range of the developed method was $911\text{-}4556 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for methanol, $1513\text{-}7563 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$

mL^{-1} for acetone, $1498\text{-}7489 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for isopropyl alcohol, $192\text{-}959 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for dichloromethane, $1503\text{-}7517 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for methyl tert butyl ether, $91\text{-}456 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for n-hexane, $1517\text{-}7584 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for ethyl acetate and $1499\text{-}7495 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for n-heptane.

Figure 4: Linearity chromatograms of LDT residual solvents Solvent Names: a) methanol b) acetone c) isopropyl alcohol d) dichloromethane e) methyl ter. butyl ether f) n-hexane g) ethyl acetate h) n-heptane

Accuracy (recovery)

The method's accuracy was determined by spiking all solvents at various levels, including the LOQ level, 100% level, and 150% level relative to the test concentration. Accuracy at the LOQ level was verified by injecting three separate preparations of LDT spiked with each residual solvent at the LOQ level and calculating the percentage recoveries of each solvent. All LOQ level specimen chromatograms were shown in Figure 3. Recovery for all solvents was found between 80–120%. Recovery study and method precision results indicate that the method was accurate. The accuracy data is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Accuracy data of residual solvents in LDT

Solvent Name	% Recovery at			
	*LOQ level	50 % level	100 % level	150 % level
Methanol	105.9	103.1	92.6	102.4
Acetone	90.8	91.2	85.5	94.8
2-Propanol	103.2	92.9	92.3	108.8
Dichloromethane	108.6	106.5	94.4	106.6
Methyl <i>tert</i> butyl ether	97.3	97.5	90.2	98.9
n-Hexane	89.7	94.2	84.0	94.2
Ethyl acetate	94.1	92.4	86.2	97.4
n-Heptane	108.2	107.3	98.5	110.0

* LOQ: Limit of quantitation

Precision

The precision of the method verified by system precision and method precision. System precision is analyzed by six imitate injections of solvent standard solution and method precision performed by six varied preparation of spike solution. In both studies % RSD found as less than 10.0%. The precision data is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Precision data of residual solvents in LDT

Solvent Name	*LOQ level	% ^RSD at	
		100 % level	150 % level
Methanol	2.22	2.2	4.0
Acetone	3.25	3.25	4.7
2-Propanol	5.90	5.90	9.7
Dichloromethane	3.91	3.91	6.0
Methyl <i>tert</i> butyl ether	4.50	4.50	7.1
n-Hexane	4.98	4.98	7.6
Ethyl acetate	4.03	4.03	7.0
n-Heptane	4.86	4.86	8.7

* LOQ: Limit of quantitation

^ RSD: Related standard deviation

System suitability

The system suitability criterion considered for the resolution of closely eluting peaks like acetone

and isopropyl alcohol is not less than 1.0. The system suitability verified before starting the each validation parameter and resolution found as 2.5. The specimen chromatogram of shown in Figure 1. and other system suitability parameters were shown in Table 6.

Table 6: System suitability data of residual solvents in LDT

Solvent Name	Resolution	Tailing factor
Methanol	0.00	1.79
Acetone	19.18	1.04
2-Propanol	2.33	1.01
Dichloromethane	4.60	1.05
Methyl <i>tert</i> butyl ether	3.11	1.02
n-Hexane	3.00	1.00
Ethyl acetate	12.77	1.00
n-Heptane	14.95	0.96

Robustness

Robustness study performed by slightly changing HSGC parameters like, carrier gas flow rate and oven temperature. The oven temperature ± 3 °C from the initial conditions and the flow rate $\pm 5\%$ from the initial conditions. The absence of notable variances in % RSD, resolution, and elution order indicates the robustness of the method.

Batch analysis

The batch analysis was conducted using the validated method for two lab verification batches of LDT. During the batch analysis, the system suitability complies as per the validation parameters and other batch analysis results were reported in Table 7.

Table 7: Batch Analysis data of residual solvents in LDT

Batch Analysis			
Solvent name	Specification	Results (LDT-DS/U-066/001)	Results (LDT-DS/U-049/173)
Methanol	3000 ppm	Below [#] LOD	2222 ppm
Acetone	5000 ppm	Below [#] LOD	3351 ppm
Isopropyl alcohol	5000 ppm	4402 ppm	17.8 ppm
Dichloromethane	600 ppm	Below [#] LOD	21.8 ppm
Methyl <i>tert</i> butyl ether	5000 ppm	Below [#] LOD	Below [#] LOD
n-Hexane	290 ppm	1 ppm	Below [#] LOD
Ethyl acetate	5000 ppm	140 ppm	140 ppm
n-Heptane	5000 ppm	Below [#] LOD	Below [#] LOD

[#]LOD : Limit of detection

CONCLUSION

An expedient and discriminating static Headspace Gas Chromatography (HSGC) methodology has been assessed for the precise quantification of solvents including acetone, isopropyl alcohol, dichloromethane, n-hexane, ethyl acetate, isopropyl acetate, and n-heptane in LDT. This method,

developed with careful consideration of synthesis routes and solvent properties, exhibits specificity, resilience, linearity, and accuracy. Notably, its utility extends beyond LDT to encompass the analysis of residual solvents in diverse settings. It is well-suited for routine and in-process quality control analyses across different manufacturing contexts. We are confident in the precision, affordability, and commercial viability of this demonstrated quantitative technique in LDT, which also holds promise for large-scale industrial manufacturing applications.

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DECLARATION

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest. This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by any of the authors.

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